

Teachers' commitment and leadership behavior as correlates of academic performance

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between students' academic performance, teachers' commitment, and leadership behavior of school administrators. Teachers' commitment was measured in two areas—commitment to job and commitment to organization and the leadership behavior of school administrators were evaluated in terms of consideration and initiating structure. Eighty-one teachers, 11 school heads, and 470 students served as respondents. The descriptive survey research technique, correlation analysis, and the following statistical methods were used: frequency, mean, standard deviation, and correlation coefficient. The study revealed that the initiating structure and consideration dimensions of leadership behavior affect teachers' commitment to job (CTJ) and teacher's commitment to organization (CTO). The correlation between CTJ and CTO and leadership behavior-initiating structure is positive and with leadership behavior-consideration negative. CTJ and CTO is correlated with the students' academic performance in math, but not in Science and English. The correlation is negative. Students' academic performance in all subject areas is negatively correlated with leadership behavior-initiating structure and has no significant relationship with leadership behavior-consideration. The leadership behavior-initiating structure is positively correlated with teachers' commitment to both job and organization but has negative correlation with students' academic performance in math, science, and English.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One area in education that has been the subject of frequent investigation is students' academic performance. Generally speaking, such studies determine how to make teaching more effective and efficient to improve learning. Educators continuously determine how best teaching can be delivered to improve learning quality.

Academic performance is used as the unit of measurement of student achievement in any course of study. It (academic performance) is a measurable and observable behavior of students within a specific period or school term. It is measured by the students' scores in different assessment forms [1], [2]. Despite criticisms that they are not the best way to measure academic performance, scores obtained in examinations, particularly standardized tests, remain the primary method of evaluating student achievement. One study

emphasized that academic performance involves meeting goals, achievements, and objectives set in the program or course that students are enrolled in and attend, expressed through grades resulting from an assessment that involves passing or not specific tests, subjects, or courses [3].

Studies conducted on students' performance in the classroom examined or evaluated how certain factors or variables related to school, teachers, school administrators, or students and their environment affect academic achievement. Some studies focus only on one variable, and some combine two or more. While numerous variables could potentially affect students' academic performance as presented in various studies, these focusses only on constructs that are perceived to affect students' academic performance directly, namely, teachers' commitment (to their work and organization) and the leadership behavior of school administrators.

The convergence points where academic performance, teacher commitment, and leadership behavior intersect has always been an exciting area to explore. And it is important that the said area be continuously explored for the better of student learning. This study surveyed that intersection using the social exchange theory as a lens in examining the link among them. This theory describes the behavioral interaction between two or more individuals and how this behavioral interaction strengthens the behavior of the other [4]. This social interaction theory has been used in different fields of study, including sociology, psychology, and economics. It is proven to have been helpful in education as well.

Academic performance is the result of learning produced by the student and prompted by the activities of teachers. How well the students perform academically depends on how committed the teachers are to their chosen profession. On the other hand, whatever activities teachers do in a school are supposedly imposed and overseen by the school administrator. Thus, the level of commitment to job and organization the teachers manifest hinges on their supervisors' leadership behavior. Guided by the social exchange theory, the following guiding principle was created for this study: student learning is affected by teaching and teaching by management and supervision performed by school leaders.

Teachers play the most crucial role in student achievement. Everything that transpires in the classroom, particularly learning, is affected mainly by the teachers' characteristic traits, beliefs, and modes of teaching [5]. When academic performance is unsatisfactory, everybody in the academe looks to the teachers' direction. The teachers usually take the blame when the students fail in academic expectations. It is almost impossible for teachers to escape from the notion that "when students did not learn, the teacher did not teach." While there may be no empirical evidence proving that that is true, there is also no evidence to the contrary. However, whether that notion is true or otherwise, it is clear that professionalism dictates that teachers should commit to their duties and responsibilities as teachers and to the organization where they belong. It is not only to their job that teachers are expected to display commitment but also to the school organization. Commitment to job and commitment to organization are constructs that are related to one another but different in some ways. In the school setting, while job commitment relates to the teacher's dedication and attachment to their profession, organizational commitment pertains to the teacher's loyalty to the school as an organization.

As previously mentioned, numerous variables could influence academic outcomes. However, out of the many factors that could affect learning, the teacher arguably has the most substantial impact [6]. Perhaps, the teacher-related factors have a more significant impact than any other factors including those related to school administrators or leaders. Other researchers agreed with the assertion that faculty do matter. They explained that the educational context created by faculty behaviors and attitudes dramatically affects student learning and engagement [7], [8].

Effective leadership practices are indispensable in contributing to student achievement. School leaders are expected to create a conducive learning environment [9]. Nevertheless, even when leadership fails and the schools cannot provide all the required facilities, learning objectives can be achieved when teachers fully commit to their job. Among the characteristics ascribed to teachers, researchers claim that the most important is commitment. Improving school performance and attaining quality education requires a high commitment to teaching [10]. If teachers are held responsible when students are not performing well, should somebody take responsibility when teachers are not teaching the way they should, thus resulting in poor academic performance?

The teachers supervise the students in the class. They manage the teaching-learning process. Conversely, someone supervises the teachers and manages the school's operations in general. They are the leaders supervising the school operations. In the case of this study, these leaders are referred to as school administrators. The kind of leadership they manifest affects the performance of both the teachers and the students—the former directly and the latter indirectly. Among teachers, commitment develops, or strengthens as they work under the supervision of the school leader. The better the leader, the more committed the teachers become. That commitment emerges or evolves depending on the leadership behavior they experience firsthand.

Leadership is a construct that has been defined in many ways. It was reported that this concept has more than 350 definitions. Leadership is a prominent power relationship in which the leader effectively affects actions and changes among followers [11]. Foremost among the functions of leadership is goal setting. All the other things a leader must do are geared towards achieving the goals set or desired outcome. This study looks at leadership as a process in which an individual influence a group to achieve and commit to a common goal.

The primary objective of school administrators is clear inspire and motivate school personnel towards improving students' academic performance through which the effectiveness of the school as an organization will be measured. The school administrator must ensure that teachers become and remain committed to their job and the school. Leadership style has often been considered one of the vital factors that can enhance employee commitment and is seen as the live wire for attaining organizational goals [12]. The success of any academic program hinges on the leadership skills of school leaders.

School administrators know too well how their leadership quality would make the teachers want to stay and be committed to the organization. It was argued that when employees desire to leave an organization, it reflects whether they perceive their leaders as efficient and supportive [13]. The perception of efficiency and supportiveness among leaders constitute the two kinds of leadership behavior this study looks into – task-oriented and people-oriented. Which leadership behaviors would more effectively motivate teachers to perform at their best to help students improve their academic performance?

Leaders in both the academic and corporate worlds can be task- or relationship-focused. They can either be task-oriented or relationship-oriented. When heads of organizations are more concerned with the satisfaction, motivation, and well-being of the people they lead, they are labeled democratic. Conversely, when managers or supervisors concern themselves more with the work to be done than the welfare of the organization's members, they are classified as autocratic. Laissez-faire is acknowledged as the third type of leadership. This style reflects organizations' "non-leadership" state and is universally considered the most ineffective leadership style [14].

In the literature on leadership styles and behaviors, democratic leadership is also described as transformational, while autocratic leadership is referred to as transactional. In the widely used and known leadership instrument the leadership behavior description questionnaire (LBDQ) the task-oriented behavior of leaders is labeled as "initiating structure" and the people-oriented behavior "consideration" [15]. Transactional leaders who focus on the structured aspects of leadership are often associated with the former, while transformational leaders are perceived as supportive and friendly with the latter.

How the leadership behavior exhibited by the managers of schools influences academic achievement cannot be taken for granted. However, there is an argument that leadership is second only to teaching in its impact on student learning. High-quality leaders best impact students by setting directions, ensuring the organization functions, and developing people. A school manager plays an important role in ensuring good academic achievement. They are tasked in creating a climate that promotes excellence in teaching and learning. They must exert both instructional and transformational leadership [16]. It remains unknown what kinds of school leadership behaviors effectively improve teachers' performance and academic achievement [17]. This research focuses on the not often used consideration and initiating structure dimensions of leadership behavior to examine their relationship with teacher commitment and students' academic performance. Moreover, while most studies investigated teacher commitment generally, this one probed into teachers' commitment to job (CTJ) and teacher's commitment to organization (CTO) separately. A better understanding of students' academic performance can be achieved by examining teachers' commitment to their job and organization and determining which dimension of leadership behavior consideration or initiating structure is more beneficial to students' academic performance and teacher commitment.

While it is widely acknowledged that school leadership plays a second fiddle to teacher commitment as far as the impact on student's academic performance is concerned, there are more studies on how the leadership behavior of school leaders affects learning than how teachers' commitment influences the same. This is one concern that this study attempted to address. Li *et al.* [18] reiterated that "the effect of school leadership on student achievement has been extensively examined, whereas the influences of teacher commitment have not been thoroughly explored." In this study, both variables were explored, and how, as correlates, they affect learning was investigated.

The primary purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between students' academic performance and teachers' commitment and leadership behavior of school administrators. Specifically, it attempted to: i) find the level of academic performance of the students; ii) Determine the level of CTJ and CTO; iii) Identify the prevailing leadership behavior of the school heads; and iv) determine if there is a significant relationship between the following: leadership behavior of school heads, teachers' commitment, and academic performance of students. For this study, the following hypotheses were set: i) Ha1: a correlation exists between teachers' commitment and leadership behavior of school administrators;

ii) Ha2: a correlation exists between students' academic performance in math, science, and English and CTJ and CTO; and iii) Ha3: a correlation exists between students' academic performance in math, science, and English and leadership behavior of school administrators.

2. METHOD

The descriptive survey research technique was used in this study. This study is primarily a correlation analysis. Eighty-one (81) teachers, 11 school heads, and 470 students from 11 schools served as respondents. All math, science, and English teachers and heads of the respondent-schools participated in this study. Ten (10) students each were selected randomly (using the table of random numbers) from 47 graduating classes.

There were two sets of questionnaires used to gather the data needed. The instrument used to measure the level of CTJ and CTO was adapted from a similar instrument [19], while the items in the questionnaire used to determine which dimension of leadership behavior the school principals exhibit were taken from the LBDQ. The LBDQ is an instrument that measures two basic dimensions of leadership behavior, namely initiating structure or task-orientedness and consideration or people-orientedness [20]. The LBDQ classifies leaders into the following types dynamic, structured, passive, and considerate. It uses a quadrant to determine the kind of leadership is shown in Figure 1.

Figure1. LBDQ quadrants

A leader is classified “dynamic” if they get above average scores in both the initiating structure and consideration dimensions of leadership behavior (quadrant 1); “structured” if for initiating structure the score is above average but below average on consideration (quadrant 2); “passive” if on both areas the scores are below average (quadrant 3); and “considerate” if the score falls below average for “initiating structure” and above average on “consideration” (Quadrant 4).

The students' academic performance was measured through the results of their achievement tests in math, science, and English. In the questionnaire, the teacher-respondents were asked to evaluate their commitment to job and to organization guided by the following 5-point scale/interpretation: 5 strongly agree (very committed), 4 agree (committed), 3 undecideds (moderately committed), 2 disagree (uncommitted), and 1 strongly disagree (very uncommitted). They were also asked to describe the behavior of their school heads using the following scale: 5 always (behavior is manifested all the time), 4 often (behavior is manifested on most occasions), 3 occasionally (behavior is manifested every now and then but less often), 2 seldom (behavior is manifested rarely but more than never), and 1 never (behavior is not manifested at all times in any degree).

Data analysis and interpretation were made using the following statistical methods: frequency, mean, standard deviation, and correlation coefficient. Students' academic performance was measured through the achievement test results and was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The teachers' level of commitment to job and organization and the school administrators' leadership behavior were analyzed using mean. The effects of teachers' commitment and the school heads' leadership behavior on students' academic performance were analyzed using correlation. Before the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) was used for data processing. The following abbreviations were used in this study: LBDQ, CTJ, and CTO.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results of the analyses and the corresponding discussions are presented.

3.1. Teachers' commitment

The most vital ingredient in any organization's success formula is its members' commitment. Commitment is a psychological attachment to an organization in which people give their loyalty to its values and goals. Additionally, teacher commitment is the emotional bond teachers demonstrate toward their work, and it is recognized as one of the most critical factors in effective teaching [13].

Most studies that were done on teachers' commitment dealt with the following dimensions: commitment to job and organization. Commitment to job is often referred to in educational literature and studies as commitment to occupation or profession, while commitment to organization is also known as commitment to school. There are studies where professional and organizational commitment of teachers are presented as just one construct teacher commitment. In this study, the level of commitment of teacher-respondents, as perceived by themselves, was analyzed using the indicators for job commitment and organizational commitment presented in the instrument designed for this research.

The computed overall means shown in Table 1, 4.05 for CTJ and 3.99 for CTO, indicate that the teachers, as perceived by themselves, are committed to both their job and their organization. However, their commitment to job is of higher level than their commitment to organization. This is an indication that being committed to job doesn't mean being committed to their organization.

The highest individual mean scores in the category commitment to job were registered in the indicators: "I take pride in telling people that I work as a teacher;" "I prepare to work harder for the good of the teaching profession;" and "The teaching profession inspires the very best of me." In the category commitment to organization, the highest computed mean scores were tallied in the indicators: "I am prepared to work harder for the good of my school to make it more successful;" "I am proud of my school;" and "I really care about what happens to my school."

Table 1. Teachers' level of commitment to job and organization

Teachers' commitment	Overall weighted mean	Interpretation
CTJ	4.05	Committed
CTO	3.99	Committed

3.2. Leadership behavior of school administrators

School administrators do not directly deal with the students, but their leadership behavior tremendously impacts the latter's academic performance. The head of the school has always been considered crucial in improving teachers' performance and student achievement. How leadership behaviors affect the performance of both teachers and students continues to be a subject of academic studies.

This study examined the qualities of school administrators as leaders through the lens of specific leadership behaviors. Arguably, the best instrument there is to use for this purpose is the LBDQ. The said instrument dichotomizes leadership behavior only into two distinct categories. It shows whether a leader is task-oriented or people-oriented.

Table 2 shows the overall weighted mean of the leadership behavior of the school administrators in terms of the dimensions mentioned above. The computed weighted mean of 3.89 connotes that, as perceived by the teacher-respondents, the respective heads of their school's manifest, in most occasions, the qualities attributed to the leadership behavior called consideration. They view them as "willing to make changes," "friendly and approachable," and "finds time to listen to them. The highest mean values were registered in the said descriptors of the consideration dimension of leadership.

Table 2. Perceived leadership behavior of school administrators

Leadership behavior dimension	Overall weighted mean	Interpretation
Consideration	3.89	Behavior is manifested in most occasions
Initiating structure	4.23	Behavior is manifested in most occasions

Furthermore, Table 2 reveals that the school heads scored higher in the initiating structure dimension of leadership behavior (4.23), implying that the teacher-respondents perceived them to manifest such behavior on most occasions. The teachers think their leaders encourage using uniform procedures, trying new ideas with them, and asking them to follow standard rules and regulations. The foregoing are the descriptors of the initiating structure dimension that got the highest mean scores.

Leaders can be perceived to manifest one of the two dimensions of leadership behavior. However, it does not follow that they do not show the characteristics indicative of the other dimension. A leader may

manifest one dimension of leadership behavior more strongly. When the computed mean for the scores of each school administrator on the two dimensions of leadership behavior was plotted on the LBDQ quadrants as shown in Figure 2, it revealed that the heads of the schools are high in both “initiating structure” and “consideration.” The mean scores intersecting in quadrant 1 indicate that they manifest behaviors characteristic of a “dynamic leader.” However, they scored higher in “initiating structure” than on “consideration,” which means that the school leaders are more “task-oriented” than “people-oriented.”

After computing the average mean scores in both dimensions of leadership behavior (initiating structure and consideration) for each school administrator and plotting them in the LBDQ quadrant, the horizontal and vertical lines drawn intersected in quadrants 1 and 2, as shown in Figure 2. As previously mentioned, the result of the quadrant plotting implies that as perceived by the teacher-respondents, their administrators as leaders are either structured or dynamic, although more on the former. None were either passive or considerate. Most administrators exhibit behaviors attributed to structured leadership, which implies that they are high in initiating structure but low in consideration, while the rest manifest behaviors that characterize dynamic leaders high in initiating structure and consideration.

Figure 2. The computed mean for the scores of the school heads plotted on the LBDQ quadrants

3.3. Academic performance of students

Students' academic performance is one of the most (if not the most) researched topics in education and related fields. Educators and researchers have been exploring variables and constructs contributing to students' performance quality. They have identified numerous factors that influence learning outcomes, two of which are examined in this study teacher commitment and leadership behavior.

While grades or scores in examinations or tests are not the only way to measure academic success, they have remained the most objective way of evaluating academic performance. In this study, students' academic performance is measured through their performance in an annual achievement test for students in the respondent schools. Table 3 shows the academic performance of students in the subjects of math, science, and English. These are the results of their achievement tests in the subject areas.

Table 3. Academic performance of students measured through their achievement test scores

Scores (English)	Frequency	%	Scores (math)	Frequency	%	Scores (science)	Frequency	%
39-41	2	0.43	40-44	19	4.04	29-31	2	0.43
36-38	25	5.32	35-39	22	4.68	26-28	6	1.28
33-35	44	9.36	30-34	30	6.38	23-25	22	4.68
30-32	86	18.30	25-29	37	7.87	20-22	63	13.40
27-29	87	18.51	20-24	92	19.57	17-19	118	25.11
24-26	91	19.36	15-19	151	32.13	14-16	113	24.04
21-23	71	15.11	10-14	104	22.13	11-13	109	23.19
18-20	34	7.23	5-9	14	2.98	8-10	33	7.02
15-17	19	4.04	0-4	1	0.21	5-7	3	0.64
12-14	10	2.13				2-4	1	.021
9-11	1	0.21						
Total	470	100	Total	470	100	Total	470	100
Mean=26.66	Mean=20.23	Mean=16.00	Mean=26.66	Mean=20.23	Mean=16.00	Mean=26.66	Mean=20.23	Mean=16.00
SD=5.71	SD=8.35	SD=4.26	SD=5.71	SD=8.35	SD=4.26	SD=5.71	SD=8.35	SD=4.26

The computed mean and standard deviation (SD) in math are 20.23 and 8.35, respectively, which implies that the scores of the students in the said subject area range from 11.88 to 28.88. As indicated by the computed mean, the average score in science is 16, and the SD of 4.26 implies that the students have scores that fall within the range of 11.74 to 20.26. The computed mean for the English subject area indicates an average score of 26.66. A SD 5.71 implies that the 470 students have scores that fall within the range of 20.95 to 32.37.

3.4. Correlation analyses

The correlation analyses reveal that teachers' commitment and leadership behavior of school administrators are significantly correlated. As shown in Table 4, the two forms of teachers' commitment used in this study, namely commitment to job and commitment to organization, registered the highest correlation coefficient $r = 0.887$, sig. < 0.01 . The two dimensions of leadership behaviors initiating structure and consideration also have a relatively high correlation coefficient at $r = 0.733^{**}$.

Table 4. Correlation coefficient between teachers' commitment and leadership behavior of school administrators

	CTJ	CTO	Initiating structure	Consideration
CTJ	1	0.887**	0.166**	-0.239**
CTO		1	0.146**	-0.302**
Initiating structure			1	0.733**
Consideration				1

** Significant at the 0.01 level, * Significant at the 0.05 level

A positive correlation exists between leadership behavior-initiating structure and commitment to job (0.166^{**}) and commitment to organization ($r=0.146^{**}$). The correlation is negative between leadership behavior-consideration and commitment to job ($r = -0.239^{**}$) and commitment to organization ($r = -0.302^{**}$). The results of the correlation analysis have shown that the two forms of leadership behaviors are significantly related. A leader may be perceived to exhibit one of the said leadership behaviors. However, it does not imply that the leader only possesses the characteristics of one of the two. This supports the findings of studies that show that initiating structure and consideration are two separate, distinct dimensions and mutually exclusive. A high score on one does not mean a low score on the other. The leader's inclinations on one dimension may be stronger than on the other, and it is also possible that the leader manifests both characteristics on an equal level.

The correlation analyses also revealed a strong positive relationship between commitment to job and commitment to organization. The two forms of commitment complement each other, meaning that when teachers are committed to their job, they are also committed to the school organization. Job involvement and organizational commitment are closely related and interdependent. There exist no conflict between employees' commitment to their profession and their organization commitment [21]. Members of an organization who are highly invested in working there are also highly committed to their organization. This is supported by the findings of a study that concluded that teachers' organizational and professional commitments are complementary [22].

As described in this study, most school administrators, according to the teacher-respondents, are structured leaders. Studies have proven that teachers become committed to their job and organizations when principals implement structured leadership. Only teachers committed to their job and organization will thrive in this kind of leadership. In a structured leadership where leaders are more task-oriented than people-oriented, performance is planned and carefully monitored, quotas and deadlines are commonly used to motivate subordinates, and rules and regulations are enforced to pursue assigned tasks [23].

Between the leadership behavior-consideration and commitment to job and commitment to organization, the correlation is negative. This inverse relationship indicates that the more the principals exhibit this kind of leadership, the less committed to job and organization the teachers become. When leaders are more people-oriented than task-oriented, some subordinates tend to need to improve in the performance of their jobs. This corroborates the findings in a study that assert that the task-oriented behavioral leadership style is effective [24] and negates the finding in a separate study that indicates that the major limitation associated with task-oriented leadership is what it usually results in stress among employees and their loss of commitment [25].

As can be gleaned from Table 5, a negative correlation exists between the students' performance in math and CTJ ($r = -0.126^{**}$) and CTO ($r = -0.189^{**}$). The inverse relationship indicates that the more committed the teachers are to their job and organization, the lower the students' math scores. However, the

size of the correlation coefficient is considered negligible. There is no correlation between students' performance in Science and English and CTJ and CTO.

Table 5. Correlation coefficient between teachers' commitment, leadership behavior of principals, and students' academic performance

	Math	Science	English
CTJ	-0.126**	-0.033	-0.050
CTO	-0.189**	-0.050	-0.067
Initiating structure	-0.209**	-0.094*	-0.126**
Consideration	-0.073	0.032	-0.038

** Significant at the 0.01 level, * Significant at the 0.05 level

Correlation analyses show no existing relationship between leadership behavior consideration and the students' performance in math, science, and English. However, the results are different from the other dimension of leadership behavior. Leadership behavior initiating structure is negatively correlated with math ($r = -.209^{**}$), science ($r = -.094^{*}$), and English ($r = -.126^{**}$). This means that the more a school administrator exhibits the behavior of this kind of leader, the lower the students' scores in those subject areas will be. The level of negative relationships, however, is considered negligible.

The results of this study reveal a negative correlation between teacher commitment and students' math performance. The findings of another study [26] indicate a different result. The correlation between teachers' commitment and the performance of students in math is positive. That study concluded that as teachers' organizational commitment increases, their level of performance is also strengthened. Moreover, as teachers perform well, the pupils are motivated, thus, developing a positive attitude toward the subject. Most studies show a positive correlation between students' academic performance and teachers' commitment [22], [27]. In general, teacher commitment is positively linked to students' academic achievement. As observed in 14 research literature, a positive correlation exists between teacher commitment and students' academic achievement. Conversely, only two research studies showed a negative correlation [28].

The negative correlation between student performance and the initiating structure dimension of leadership manifested by the school administrator may be considered negligible. However, it is worth noting that the inverse relationship was observed between the said dimension of leadership and the students' performance not only in one of the subject areas but in all.

The students are not directly affected by any leadership style school administrators display but rather by the teachers. When leaders score higher in leadership behavior initiating structure dimension, they are task-oriented. This dimension of leadership is not known to influence the teachers to deliver an optimum performance positively. This could explain why when school heads exhibit this brand of leadership, the students' scores in the subject areas will be lower. It was concluded in a study [29] that task-oriented leader squelches innovation and creativity and create a tense work environment, so the required results of improving the organization's performance cannot be achieved. Somehow, these findings were negated. A researcher [30] investigated the influence of principals' leadership behavior on students' performance in a certification examination. They found that the principals scored higher in consideration than initiating structure. As regards students' performance, it was generally described in the study as below average. Consequently, they recommended that in-service training be given to the principals to train them to strike a balance between the leadership dimensions consideration and initiating structure, indirectly indicating that students tend to perform better when principals are more task-oriented as a leader rather than people-oriented. A similar study [31] revealed that headteachers were rated significantly higher in initiating structure than in consideration dimension. The researcher pointed out that there was a significant positive relationship between the headteachers' leadership behavior and students' academic performance.

A study concluded that both dimensions of leadership behavior-initiating structure and consideration positively influence student performance [32]. Task-oriented leaders scoring higher in the initiating structure dimension are considered autocratic. Leaders who focus on tasks that should be carried out to reach goals can be described as autocratic [33]. Conversely, people-oriented leaders who score higher in the consideration dimension are perceived as transformational leaders. Transformational leadership is attached to people-oriented decision-making styles [34]. The study's overall result indicated that transformational leadership and autocratic styles were utilized in the respondent schools more than in other styles. The study revealed that students performed well and that both teachers and students were satisfied with their school administrators, and their performing well is a direct reflection of leadership styles.

4. CONCLUSION

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This study was conducted to find out if there is a significant relationship between leadership behavior of principals, CTJ and CTO, and students' academic performance. The study established that both forms of leadership behavior of the school heads (initiating structure and consideration) affect CTJ and CTO. Therefore, Ha1 (there exists a correlation between teachers' commitment and leadership behavior of school administrators) is accepted. The correlation between both aspects of teachers' commitment and the initiating structure dimension of leadership behavior is positive. With the consideration dimension, the correlation is negative. This inverse relationship implies that the less committed teachers to both their job and organization become when the heads of their schools manifest a more people-oriented behavior than task-oriented. There is a need to conduct studies parallel to this to verify these findings.

One probable reason for teachers becoming more committed to their job and organization when the school leader is task-oriented is clarity. Leaders who are strong in "initiating structure" are arguably more precise and specific with their expectations and goals than their people-oriented counterparts. In this study, the teacher-respondents may happen to prefer leaders who are task-oriented more than those who are people-oriented. The teachers respond more positively to a structured style of leadership. But as previously articulated, being task-oriented does not necessarily mean that the leaders are not concerned about the well-being of those they lead. As the findings of this study have shown, the teachers perceive the school managers as "dynamic," which means that they scored above average in both dimensions of leadership behavior only that they manifest more strongly the leadership behavior "initiating structure." Scoring above average in both dimensions indicates flexibility for the school leaders. They were able to adapt their strategies and approaches based on the needs and circumstances, which is crucial in helping maintain or enhance teacher commitment. Thus, in this study, teachers were found to be committed to both their job and organization.

It is only with the students' performance in math, not science and English that CTJ and CTO are correlated (negatively). Therefore, Ha2 (A correlation exists between students' academic performance in math, science, and English and CTJ and CTO). is accepted only for the subject area of math. As mentioned in the previous section, findings of most similar studies, show a positive correlation between students' academic performance and teachers' commitment. Rarely was in studies that a negative correlation between teachers' commitment and student performance was shown. That negative relationship was established in this study. However, in this study, the size of the (negative) correlation coefficient between the abovementioned variables is considered negligible.

Despite the rarity of seeing a negative correlation between teacher commitment and students' academic performance, its occurrence is still disconcerting. It is counterintuitive to find that when teachers show commitment to their jobs, students' academic performance suffers. Certain circumstances or strategies committed teachers apply could negatively impact students' academic performance. Teachers could overly commit to academic undertakings and high standards that inadvertently create excessive pressure and stress for students, possibly leading to burnout and anxiety. Such could result in reduced performance on the part of the students. When teachers become overly committed, they may fail to balance work and life, leading to burnout that may diminish their ability to deliver quality instruction and engage students more productively.

Students' performance in all subject areas is negatively correlated with leadership behavior-initiating structure and has no significant relationship with leadership behavior-consideration. Therefore, Ha3 (A correlation exists between students' academic performance in math, science, and English and leadership behavior of school administrators.) is accepted only for leadership behavior-initiating structure.

A negative correlation exists between students' academic performance in math, science, and English and the "initiating structure" leadership behavior of school administrators. Although the size of the (negative) correlation coefficient is considered negligible, it is interesting to note is that while the initiating structure dimension of leadership behavior is positively correlated to teacher commitment, it is the other way around with the academic performance of students, and not only in one subject area but all. One possible reason for such an inverse relationship is that the task-oriented approach of school leaders can indirectly put too much burden on students, thus negatively impacting their performance. They can overly emphasize strict academic goals that could create high-stress environments in the schools they supervise. It may have positively impacted teacher commitment but affected the students' performance negatively. The academic pressure created when students are forced to adhere to the strict standards that task-oriented heads of schools set could negatively impact their well-being. They may experience burnout, which could affect their academic performance.

Additionally, when school heads are task-oriented, they tend to give more attention to curricular activities and less to non-academic ones. Extracurricular activities are known to benefit students. They can positively impact the students' academic performance, mental health, and well-being. The "all work and no (or less) play" that task-oriented heads of schools tend to implement may not be helping students perform better academically.

As shown in this study, the leadership behavior-initiating structure of school leaders is positively correlated to CTJ and CTO but negatively correlates with students' academic performance. Perhaps studies can be done to probe deeper into this. The primary objective of the study is to answer the question "Does initiating structure dimension of leadership behavior positively affect CTJ and organization and negatively influence the academic performance of students?"

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